

Industries of Ideas Technical Brief

Research Domain Clustering & Labeling: Overview & Initial Validation*

Jason Owen-Smith
Institute for Research on Innovation & Science (IRIS)
University of Michigan
jdos@umich.edu

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<https://industriesofideas.ai>

Abstract

The Industries of Ideas project prioritizes people rather than documents in its analytic approach. Nevertheless, the US science funding system overwhelmingly supports projects, not people. Thus, our efforts to characterize research investments in Critical and Emerging Technologies (CETs) sometimes require document level work without loss of fidelity to our larger conceptual framework.

Industries of Ideas seeks to develop timely, actionable, trustworthy, local data about the regional effects CETs such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) are having on jobs, employers, education, earnings, and skills in local. We do this work in close collaboration with stakeholders and decision-makers to identify questions of immediate concern and co-develop the data products that can provide useful insight. As such, assessments of AI research investments and their implications must often focus on substantive domains where AI tools and methods are being applied with a level of granularity that cannot currently be reliably achieved using existing classification systems.

This technical brief outlines a new method for robust clustering and labeling of large scale scientific and technical data that relies on hybrid social and semantic embeddings, unsupervised machine learning models, and human in the loop multi-agent LLM summarization to address that need across multiple CETs. It outlines the clustering method, its analytic alignment with Industries of Idea’s person-centric conceptual and methodological framework, and presents initial algorithmic validation findings using two public document corpora, 78,355 funded US National Science Foundation (NSF) grants, and 120,955 physics articles published in American Physical Society (APS) journals.

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Introducing the Challenge

Substantive Needs

Higher resolution on the contents of research investments is needed for many questions. Industries of Ideas’ state-led efforts to examine the relationship between innovation-driven technological change and regional workforce dynamics may focus on relationships between specific research domains and particular industries. Education and training providers, workforce agencies, or employers (1) might wish to use the contents of frontier research projects to suggest the directions that technology is heading with an eye toward leapfrogging programs ahead of the curve of local labor market conditions.

Research and economic development leaders may wish to identify distinctive areas of strength to support strategic efforts aimed at emerging opportunities. Finally, science funders and innovation leaders may be concerned with identifying risk and redundancy in complex portfolios that often span many performers and investors. All these use cases would require much greater granularity in assessing the contents of AI grants than is currently within easy reach.

Technical Barriers

The challenge is scale. When dealing with hundreds of thousands or millions of technical documents across many fields of research, it is all but impossible to make systematic sense of content variations absent some heuristic or algorithmic tool. Heuristically, one might characterize grants based on the most fine-grained information available about their funders.

For instance, public NSF and NIH grants data allows program or study section information to broadly characterize the topic areas of awards. Such data are not available for all, or even most funders, though. As important, relying on them would make efforts to characterize research investments in particular technologies across agencies or types of investors difficult.

Algorithmic approaches could be mobilized. Significant work to topic model and cluster documents using a variety of approaches have long been a common component of evaluation, analytics and research about science and technology. Yet recent work is beginning to demonstrate that even sophisticated, Large Language Model (LLM)-based approaches can struggle to recreate well established classification systems (2). Clustering efforts that rely on the structure of networks of citations or other connections among documents such as hyperlinks (3) have gained traction. More recently, approaches that combine document links and textual embeddings in various ways have shown promise (4–6).

Taking these approaches as an inspiration, we propose a new method for clustering scientific documents, which we initially validate using known classifications for NSF grants and physics papers. We mobilize a hybrid embedding approach that integrates links among documents and rich transformer based semantic embeddings. To these we add social connections among projects and people that documents represent.

We thus align document level work to identify granular application domains for CETs such as AI with the person-centric (7, 8), social and “invisible college” (9) driven sensibility that underlies the Industries of Ideas approach to research field identification. That focus takes researchers as a starting point and treats the problem of identifying the boundaries and current contents of an evolving technology field as a species of community identification problem. The work being done here is no different, though its focus is, conceptually, on partitioning a larger field into meaningful subdivisions rather than on differentiating it from other arenas.

We take now classic work in social science that examines the characteristics of communities, fields and networks (10–12) as a starting point and integrate insights drawn from it with with more contemporary natural language processing (13) and network science (14, 15) tools. Our focus is on augmenting the value of document-level textual relationships by adding social signals of similarity derived from relationships among authors or investigators through mechanisms such as social proximity, affinity, signaling and attention (16–18)

Initial results have been promising, especially when coupled with a new approach to cluster summarization that enables us to efficiently develop and improve means to tag the results of granular document clustering using human readable labels. This labeling relies on prompt-based summarization of clustered text in a simple multi-agent framework with very light human review to ensure continued improvement and usability.

As a preliminary step toward full development and validation, this technical brief:

1. Summarizes the conceptual and technical approach
2. Presents an overview of the data and clustering pipeline
3. Reports preliminary validation findings from a clustering of the corpus of NSF awards
4. Describes and qualitatively assesses the prompt-based cluster summarization tool.

Conceptual Approach.

Industries of Ideas’ overarching framework treats science and technology research areas as communities defined by reliance on similar resources, stable patterns of collaboration and competition, broadly shared formal and informal “rules of the game” and distinctive, often specialized languages for describing their work and interests (19). We operationalize this framework using a hybrid vector embedding strategy that concatenates multiple social and textual embeddings to capture several dimensions of this social, community-based definition of science and technology fields.

More specifically, we cluster grants based on proximities in a vector space defined by three network layers and one semantic layer. This approach builds on the intuition that both similarities between the text of documents and observable connections created by the activities of the people who create them are important to understanding how the ideas they contain diffuse, combine, and “hang together” to represent coherent areas of research (9, 20). Industries of Ideas anchors unsupervised clustering methods on a data pipeline that highlights both the social and the textual connections among grants. The four data layers we construct and embed capture different aspects of this approach.

Network layer 1 captures the idea of shared membership and common activities represented by affinity and signaling mechanisms connecting grants through acknowledgment of common papers and patents and papers which are published in the same venues..

Network layer 2 connects grants that share the same PI in recognition that research programs often require support across multiple projects and that, regardless of particular funders or programs and the specific language that might be mobilized to justify a specific project, work done by the same PI often represents different facets of a common program of work. Network Layer 3 is defined by publication co-authorship relationships among different grant PIs in recognition that in many highly

collaborative fields it is common to practice “rotating leadership” on grants. Finally, we vector embed the abstracts of each grant and calculate cosine distances among all grant pairs to capture the extent to which two awards deploy similar terms and language in describing their projects to provide a broad, purely LLM based textual view.

Validation Task.

Our primary substantive focus has been on classifying grants from multiple sources that are related to Artificial Intelligence. We do this using an unsupervised clustering pipeline that combines Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) dimension reduction (UMAP)(21) with Hierarchical Density Based Clustering (HDBSCAN) (22). Multiple subclustering passes followed by a three agent hierarchical summarization process result in a nested taxonomy comprised of granular “domain clusters” that sit within a smaller number of mid-level “primary categories” which in turn are nested in a small number of very general “broad groups.”

The challenge of applying such methods to a corpus of AI interdisciplinary AI related grants is that there is no clear ground truth of granular classifications against which validity checks might be made.

For validation purposes, this technical note turns to two public corpora of scientific metadata whose features make them well-suited to test the effectiveness of this clustering and labeling pipeline. We treat the NSF award corpus as a “ground truth” because the agency organizes the majority of its grant making activity around a hierarchical set of topically defined organizational units - Directorates, Divisions, and Programs. To assess whether the algorithm we are developing can be generalized beyond grants, we include a second corpus, papers published in American Physical Society journals whose PhySh codes likewise have a well-developed hierarchical classification system that runs from disciplines to a system of ‘taglike’ concepts to a single “primary concept” code.

Applying the clustering and labeling algorithm we use for AI and other CETs to these corpora provides an opportunity to test results against independent classification systems for two different types of documents in two different use cases. The first, NSF, represents a structure where investigators target (and tailor) proposals to meet the interests programs specify in calls and enforce through the selection of reviewers and program officers. The second, APS, represents a system developed by a disciplinary publisher that authors use to categorize their works for discovery and consumption by colleagues. For our purposes, the NSF corpus represents a test of whether the algorithm can distinguish among broadly interdisciplinary categories at different levels of granularity. In contrast, the APS case represents a test of the algorithm’s ability to discern more fine-grained subfield distinctions within a large discipline.

Expectations.

A strong unsupervised clustering approach will approximate the organizational structure of NSF in its outputs. Grants supported by the same program should be most proximate to each other in the hybrid embedding space we construct and most likely to be clustered together by the model, followed by divisions and directorates. All three should be significantly closer together and likely to be jointly clustered than randomly drawn pairs of grants. Likewise we expect that the ability to capture the disciplinary and concept structure of APS PhySH codes will be evidenced by a similar pattern, greater raw proximity for pairs of papers that share more fine grained categories in common, greater likelihoods that papers with deeper taxonomical similarities will be clustered together by

the Industries of Ideas algorithm, and qualitative overlap between LLM assigned cluster labels and parallel topical labels assigned to their works by APS authors.

Data & Method.

NSF grant data were drawn from Digital Sciences’ Dimensions corpus augmented by additional fields identifying NSF units extracted from the agency’s Fastlane corpus of public awards metadata. We examine grants made between 2020-2024. IPAs and other non-research awards were excluded as were cases where unit information was missing. Text fields were lightly cleaned to remove acronyms and other indicators of programs embedded in titles or abstracts.

APS paper data were drawn from the APS metadata corpus with abstract and citation metadata augmented via DOI linkage from Dimensions. These data cover works published from 2016-2021.

In the co-authorship network layer, cartesian fractional authorship weighting was used to accommodate the different implications of collaboration on a paper with 2 authors and one with 2000. Texts were embedded using that Allen AI Institute’s Specter2 pretrained model without fine tuning(13). Network layers were embedded using node2vec (23). Each layer was independently L2 normalized and concatenated to yield 71,388 grant by 972 dimension tensor, and a 120,955 paper by 972 dimension tensor from which cosine similarities were calculated and which provided the base input for unsupervised dimension reduction with UMAP (24) and subsequent HDBSCAN clustering (25).

Because no quantitative method for establishing best fitting parameter sets exists, model parameters were established using a coarse to fine parameter sweep evaluated across standard quality measures including silhouette score, Calini-Harabasz score, noise percentage and largest cluster concentration measures. After initial clustering, groups at the 90th percentile or larger were independently re-clustered using the same method in the interests of achieving suitable granular clusters. Clusters identified in this “second pass” were treated explicitly as sub-clusters of the original large group. Documents that did not fall into such sub-clusters remain associated with the initial “parent” cluster label in all subsequent analyses.

Preliminary Validation Findings.

Embedding Proximities.

Overall, this hybrid approach appeared to perform well in terms of embedding proximities. Figures 1a and 1b present summary information for random samples of dyads drawn from each corpus. The top two panels (Figure 1a) represent the NSF grant corpus, the bottom two (Figure 1b) the APS publication corpus. In both cases cosine similarities perform as expected. Random pairs are most distant and as shared categories become more narrow, dyads sit closer together in embedding space. Blue kernel density lines (representing grants funded by the same NSF Directorate and papers tagged with the same APS Discipline flag) are closer together than random pairs but further apart than orange same division/any concept pairs. In both cases the rank ordering of corpus native categories and embedding generated proximities aligns.

The right-hand panels reprise the finding suggested by the kernel density plots, though in slightly different ways. Figure 1a’s right hand panel presents mean similarities by organizational proximity. On average the sample of grant dyads funded by the same program have cosine similarities that

Figure 1a. Cosine Similarities by organizational proximity, NSF Grant Corpus. Left panel, Kernel Density plot for sample of N=1.2 mill dyads per line random (gray), same Directorate (blue), same Division (orange), same Program (green). Dashed vertical line = overall mean. Right panel, mean cosine similarity by organizational proximity, NSF Grant Corpus.

Figure 1b. Cosine Similarities by taxonomic similarity, APS Publication Corpus. N=1.2 million randomly sampled dyads per line. Random pairs (gray), same Discipline (blue), any Common Concept (orange), same Primary Concept (green). Dashed gray line = overall mean similarity. Right panel, mean similarity by # of common concepts, 0 with shared discipline (gray), 1 (orange) 2 or more (green).

reflect 148% more proximate positions than grant pairs that share directorates alone. Figure 1b's right hand panel takes advantage of the fact that the APS classification scheme allows for multiple concepts (though only a single primary concept) to be designated for each paper to demonstrate that those paper pairs which share more concepts in common (2+) are also closer together in embedding space, though the difference between sharing only a high level discipline flag and sharing two or more common concepts (44% more proximate) is much smaller for APS papers than it is for grants.

Indeed, the gross differences between Figure 1a and Figure 1b highlight why the two corpora together make a strong test of this clustering algorithm. The NSF grant corpus is more dispersed, overall average cosine similarity is essentially zero and at all levels of organizational proximity KDE distributions have lower peaks and wider distributions than do their APS publication counterparts. This no doubt reflects greater disciplinary variation - NSF directorates run the gamut from Biology to engineering, math to social science, education, workforce development, small business, career development, fellowship and infrastructure awards. APS papers are, at the end of the day, all journal articles about topics in physics.

Same Cluster Likelihoods.

As an additional quantitative test of the clustering algorithm, dyad-level logistic regressions were run for each corpus with a dependent variable set to 1 if a given pair of awards was assigned to the same granular cluster by the industries of Ideas algorithm. Independent variables for random samples of 7.5 million dyads drawn from each corpus indexed the same levels of organizational and taxonomic proximity reflected in Figure 1. For "full" models including dummy variables for each level of taxonomic or organizational similarity predicted probabilities across similarity scenarios enable illuminating comparisons. For instance setting all dummy variables to 0 yields an intercept only model that represents the case of a grant (or paper) dyad that shares no organizational or taxonomic similarities in common. When all dummy variables are set to 1 the scenario represents a grant pair funded by the same directorate, division and program or an APS paper tagged with the same directorate, primary, and other concept set.

Figures 2a and 2b present those predicted probabilities, which tell much the same story as the raw proximities summarized in the preceding section. For both corpora, a higher degree of similarity on NSF or APS native organizational or taxonomic categories is associated with a greater likelihood of being assigned to the same granular cluster by the unsupervised clustering algorithm. The corpora perform differently. Predicted probabilities increase much more linearly with no pronounced discontinuities between levels in the APS corpus. In contrast, the NSF corpus sees a substantial jump in the likelihood of same cluster membership for grant pairs that share a common funding program.

Finally, as a qualitative assessment of the hybrid embedding space, consider Figure 3, which presents a two-dimensional UMAP representation of the NSF corpus. Panel A colors the dots representing grants by funding directorate. Panels B & C represent divisions within the directorates of Mathematical and Physical Sciences (MPS) and Social and Behavioral Sciences (SBE) respectively.

Panel A suggests the findings presented quantitatively in Figure 1a. Distinct clusters of same color grants visually index the proximity of awards funded by the same directorates. The overall structure of the image also implies a strong starting point for further algorithm development and testing. The BIO and GEO directorates are closer to one another than either is to Computer and Information Science and Engineering (CISE) or Engineering (ENG). Parts of MPS are interspersed with ENG and others are closer to CISE. SBE sits between EDU and CISE but has clusters of grants that are more proximate to BIO. Technology, Innovation and Partnerships (TIP), in keeping with its

Figure 2a. Predicted probabilities from dyad level logistic regression on same HDBSCAN cluster membership by levels of organizational proximity for N=7.5 million randomly sampled NSF Grant dyads.

Figure 2b. Predicted probabilities from dyad level logistic regressions on same HDBSCAN cluster membership by levels of APS publication taxonomic proximity for N=7.5 million randomly sampled paper pairs.

integrative and translational mission, forms a “bridge” between otherwise separate “wings” of the image. Finally, EDU grants are largely distinct from most other NSF awards. Nevertheless, their grants are interspersed with seemingly dense pockets of projects from nearly every other directorate in a testament to the agency-wide priority given to broadening participation and STEM education efforts in the period under study.

Panels B and C add further detail that leverages the hierarchical organization of NSF’s grant making units, coloring points by funding divisions within select directorates. Here too, the results are illuminating.

Note in Panel C that the clusters of SBE awards that are very proximate to grants funded by the Biology (BIO) directorate are uniformly awarded by the division of Behavioral and Cognitive Science (BCS) as one might expect. Likewise, in Panel B, many MPS division of Mathematical Sciences (DMS) awards are clustered closer to the bulk of CISE grants while Materials Research, Chemistry, and Physics grants are more interspersed and closer to Engineering. Astronomy and some Physics grants, perhaps in testament to both fields’ reliance on major instrumentation, also have distinct clusters far removed from the body of figure.

GPT Cluster Summarization and Labeling.

The initial validation findings presented above are promising, but a key challenge remains. No matter how well the method may approximate the substantive organization of NSF grant-making or the widely used taxonomic conventions of working physicists, what it produces is a set of numeric labels that it associates with grants that share something in common. It cannot and does not reveal *what* they have in common.

Yet that is precisely the kind of insight that spurs us to pursue unsupervised clustering of the otherwise largely undifferentiated mass of “AI awards” in the first place. To begin developing the capability to cluster large numbers of awards with usable content tags for multiple purposes at scale, we are experimenting with a simple multi-agent approach to prompt based summarization and categorization of the abstracts that are included in each cluster.

The process we piloted is straightforward. We use OpenAI’s gpt-4o via the Azure API to prompt three agents in sequence with periodic human review. The first AI agent receives the clean text of a stratified sample of abstracts for grants associated with a given cluster and is prompted to provide a brief (30-50 word) summary, a cluster title of up to 5 words, ten keywords, and two general categories (primary and secondary) of science and engineering research to which the cluster might belong. In keeping with Industries of Ideas substantive focus, the prompt emphasizes non-technical summaries and focuses the agent on titles and categories that pertain to the social, economic and workforce impact of the research as well as its specific scientific implications.

Results from this initial summarization are passed to a second agent that uses them to propose a standard set of primary categories and to associate individual cluster titles with those categories. A light human review phase focused on primary category labels and cluster titles allows light editing to, for instance, address GPT’s tendency to append the words “Innovative” and “advanced” to many descriptions of scientific and technological work. Human review also ensures that labels can be lightly tuned to meet the needs of a particular use case. Finally, human reviewed category labels and associated cluster information is passed to a third agent that is prompted to generate brief definitions of the primary categories for use in prompts applied in any future refining passes to ensure continuity.

A review of the quality of the summaries and the scientific accuracy of individual titles and labels is beyond the scope of this brief. We are pursuing opportunities for expert review via work with domain experts in the course of project activities with participating states and universities. Here we follow the general validation logic set out above by conducting a preliminary qualitative assessment of this initial labeling framework. We focus on questions of alignment with the topical organization of NSF grant-making units and high level alignment with the APS taxonomy.

Figure 2. Two-Dimensional Euclidean Projection of NSF Grant Vector Embeddings. Panel A - Colored by Funding Directorate. Panel B. Colored by Division w/in MPS. Panel C. Colored by Division w/in SBE.

NSF Grant Corpus.

Thus, our efforts to characterize research investments in Critical and Emerging Technologies (CETs) sometimes require document level work without loss of fidelity to our larger conceptual framework. Industries of Ideas seeks to develop timely, actionable, trustworthy, local data about the regional effects CETs such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) are having on jobs, employers, education, earnings, and skills in local. We do this work in close collaboration with stakeholders and decision-makers to identify questions of immediate concern and co-develop the data products that can provide useful insight. As such, assessments of AI research investments and their implications must often focus on substantive domains where AI tools and methods are being applied with a level of granularity that cannot currently be reliably achieved using existing classification systems. This technical brief outlines a new method for robust clustering and labeling of large scale scientific and technical data that relies on hybrid social and semantic embeddings, unsupervised machine learning models, and human in the loop multi-agent LLM summarization to address that need across multiple CETs. It outlines the clustering method, its analytic alignment with Industries of Idea’s person-centric conceptual and methodological framework, and presents initial algorithmic validation findings using two public document corpora, 78,355 funded US National Science Foundation (NSF) grants, and 120,955 physics articles published in American Physical Society (APS) journals.

Awards in the “Life & Biosciences” category cement the remarkably close concordance between clustering, labeling and the structure of the NSF grant-making. Grants in this category are most heavily funded by the BIO directorate with substantial investments by Engineering and TIP. Panel C, which presents the specific clusters indicates how the mix of biomedical engineering, fundamental life science research, and work dedicated to the study of public impacts might lead this to be the case.

Physics Publication Corpus.

Finally, turn your attention to a final qualitative image that presents a similar visualization of the APS corpus. Figure 6a shows a 2-D representation of the relative positions of more than 122,000 physics articles colored by the most general ontology category assigned to them by their authors, the PhySH ontology Discipline code. Note first that the disciplines, which represent broad subfields of physics such as condensed matter, nuclear physics, particles & fields and quantum information, “hang together” in much the same fashion as NSF directorates and divisions appeared to.

Where Figures 1 and 2 demonstrated that embedding and clustering algorithms produced sensible geometries at the level of individual documents and dyads, Figures 3, 4, and 5b/c and 6a suggest that the more macroscopic features of the spaces that result from this hybrid social and semantic clustering approach also map fairly comfortably to established organizational and taxonomic research categorization schemes. In the case of the Figure 6a representation of Physics subfields, this is apparent in both the coherent groups of same color articles and in the proximities of related PhySH disciplines. For instance the bottom left co-location of nuclear physics, particles & fields, and gravitation, cosmology and astrophysics as well as their relative distinctiveness is sensible in both social and substantive terms (26–28)

More than simply testifying to the usefulness of the embedding space that can be created by a hybrid social and semantic approach, Figures 4b, 5 and 6b suggest the potential power of combining such methods with LLM labeling. In each case clusters identified using unsupervised machine learning tools with summarization and labeling augmentation yield directionally appropriate descriptors of existing organizational categories for NSF grants that also map onto established flows of resources. Figure 6d demonstrates that the same methods appear capable, at least in broad terms, of mapping

Figure 4. Two-Dimensional Euclidean Projection of NSF Grant Vector Embeddings. Panel A – Colored by Funding Directorate. Panel B – Colored by LLM generated and human reviewed cluster category label.

Figure 5. Cross-Directorate Research Category Examples. Panel A - Heatmap of funding intensity, category X directorate. Panel B - Cluster colored grants within Energy, Infrastructure and Communications category. Panel C – Cluster colored grants within Life & Biosciences category.

subfield distinctions within a single well-established disciplinary ontology used by authors as well.

Consider Figure 6b and note the strong alignment between the LLM generated labels and the PhySH discipline codes applied to the same quadrants of Figure 6a. The large yellow cluster in 6a “Condensed Matter Physics” is an LLM labeled group (orange) called “Condensed Matter & Quantum Materials” in Figure 6b. The top panel’s dark green “Nuclear Physics” is reprised in the lower panel’s pink “Nuclear, Hadronic and Dense Matter” group, which like it’s taxonomic alter-ego above sits adjacent to a particle physics research cluster that is translated via LLM as “Particles, Fields and Accelerators.”

Figure 6a. UMAP 2-D Scatterplot of APS Corpus. Dots represent articles colored by PhySH Discipline Codes.

Figure 6b. UMAP 2-D Scatterplot of the APS Corpus. Dots represent articles colored by LLM assigned Industries of Ideas Broad Group classification.

In other words, the more qualitative and holistic aspects of validation presented in this section would seem to suggest that the combination of social and semantic clustering and LLM summarization has real promise for producing both broadly valid and at least directionally accurate characterizations of the geometry and the content of fields where the true shape of applications are currently unknown. In fields like AI where even broad differentiation into application domains could be of immediate

value to decision makers in many areas, the impact could be substantial.

Overall, this closer look at means to label clusters at scale reinforces the initial promise of the clustering approach itself and offers strong qualitative support for the validity of a multi-agent summarization and labeling pipeline. The strong initial performance of these tools on two very different research corpora with established but varied classification schemes suggests a reasonable degree of confidence can be taken in both the clustering and labeling results for cases, like our application in AI, where such “ground truth” is absent. Significant work remains to be done, including detailed and systematic expert validation and more rigorous testing against additional comparison cases, but these preliminary findings suggest important routes for pursuing just such work.

References.

1. J. Owen-Smith, “AI and Work: How to Build New Data Foundations” (2024).
2. I. Constantino, S. Kojaku, S. Fortunato, Y.-Y. Ahn, Representing the disciplinary structure of physics: A comparative evaluation of graph and text embedding methods. *Quantitative Science Studies* **6**, 263–280 (2025).
3. V. A. Traag, L. Waltman, N. J. Van Eck, From Louvain to Leiden: guaranteeing well-connected communities. *Sci. Rep.* **9**, 1–12 (2019).
4. A. Cohan, S. Feldman, I. Beltagy, D. Downey, D. S. Weld, SPECTER: Document-level Representation Learning using Citation-informed Transformers. (2020).
5. M. Yasunaga, J. Leskovec, P. Liang, LinkBERT: Pretraining Language Models with Document Links. (2022).
6. Y. Zhang, X. Chen, B. Jin, S. Wang, S. Ji, W. Wang, J. Han, A Comprehensive Survey of Scientific Large Language Models and Their Applications in Scientific Discovery. (2024).
7. J. Owen-Smith, “Will the Real AI Researcher Please Stand Up? Fields, Networks and Systems to Measure the Impact of Research Investments” in *New Approaches to Characterize Industries: AI as Framework and Use Case* (American Enterprise Institute).
8. J. Owen-Smith, “Person-Centric AI Research Community Identification: Initial Seed Set Validation *” (2026); <https://doi.org/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.20425418.svg>.
9. D. Crane, *Invisible Colleges: Diffusion of Scientific Knowledge* (University of Chicago Press, Chicago IL, 1972).
10. M. Granovetter, “Economic Action and Social Structure: The Problem of Embeddedness” *American Journal of Sociology.* **91**, 481–510 (1985).
11. A. Portes, Social Capital: Its Origins and Applications in Modern Sociology. *Annu. Rev. Sociol.* **24** (1998).
12. W. W. Powell, D. R. White, K. W. Koput, J. Owen-Smith, Network dynamics and field evolution: The growth of interorganizational collaboration in the life sciences. *American Journal of Sociology* **110**, 1132–1205 (2005).
13. A. Cohan, S. Feldman, I. Beltagy, D. Downey, D. S. Weld, SPECTER: Document-level Representation Learning using Citation-informed Transformers. (2020).

14. M. E. J. Newman, Modularity and community structure in networks. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **103**, 8577–8582 (2006).
15. M. E. J. Newman, M. Girvan, Finding and evaluating community structure in networks. *Phys. Rev. E Stat. Nonlin. Soft Matter Phys.* **69** (2004).
16. J. M. Podolny, Networks as the pipes and prisms of the market. *American Journal of Sociology* **10** (2001).
17. R. S. Burt, Structural Holes and Good Ideas. *American Journal of Sociology* **110**, 349–399 (2004).
18. Miller McPherson , Lynn Smith-Lovin , James M . Cook . 2001. “Birds of a Feather : Homophily in Social Networks.“ *Annual Review of Sociology* 27 (415-444).
19. A. R. R. Friedland & Robert Alford, “Bringing Society Back In: Symbols, Practices and Institutional Contradictions”. In *The New Institutionalism in Organizational Analysis* (1991).
20. U. Shwed, P. S. Bearman, The Temporal Structure of Scientific Consensus Formation. *Am. Sociol. Rev.* **75**, 817–840 (2010).
21. L. McInnes, J. Healy, J. Melville, “UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction.” (2020).
22. L. McInnes, J. Healy, S. Astels, hdbscan: Hierarchical density based clustering. *The Journal of Open Source Software* **2**, 205 (2017).
23. A. Grover, J. Leskovec, “Node2vec: Scalable feature learning for networks” in *Proceedings of the ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* Association for Computing Machinery. pp. 855–864.
24. L. McInnes, J. Healy, J. Melville, UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction. (2020).
25. L. McInnes, J. Healy, S. Astels, hdbscan: Hierarchical density based clustering. *The Journal of Open Source Software* **2**, 205 (2017).
26. P. Galison, *Image and Logic: A Material Culture of Microphysics* (University of Chicago Press, 1997).
27. K. Knorr-Cetina, *Epistemic Cultures: How the Sciences Make Knowledge* (Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA, 2009).
28. H. M. Collins, The TEA Set: Tacit Knowledge and Scientific Networks. *Soc. Stud. Sci.* **4**, 165–185 (1974).